

THE IMPORTANCE OF SPEAKING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AROUND THE WORLD

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Annotation: In this article, I will talk about how many people speak Russian in the world and the potential of teaching Russian in schools. I have given examples of the widespread promotion of the Russian language as a subject in kindergartens, schools, colleges and even higher education institutions.

Keywords: The role of the Russian language in foreign countries, human value in Russian cultures, the formation of the Russian language in children's speech, the Russian language in Uzbek schools, the culture of the Russian people, a unique worldview, national culture in Russian.

The Russian language is the national language of the Russian people and is a form of Russian national culture. The Russian language is one of the most developed languages in the world. He has a rich vocabulary and terminology, expressiveness, brevity and clarity of grammatical tools in all fields of science and technology, and the ability to reflect the diversity of things in the world. In June 2005, the Federal Law "On the State Language of the Russian Federation" was adopted. Currently, the Russian language is the fourth most widely spoken language in the world. The number one language is English, with approximately 500 million people using it as their mother tongue or as a second language. Chinese is the second most widely spoken language in the world and Spanish is the third. Everyone can think about their mother tongue or other languages at least once in their life. Works of Russian poets are used as textbooks in Uzbek schools. Have you ever thought that Uzbek language textbooks and works of Uzbek writers are taught in Russian schools?

Russian is not only the state language of the Russian Federation. This refers to the number of world languages, that is, languages that serve as a means of international communication between the peoples of different countries. Among the more than two and a half thousand languages known in the world, international communication is provided by the most developed group of world languages, which is called the World Language Club. The promotion of a language to the role of a world language is determined by the universal significance of the culture created in this language. The status of a language as a world language is legally determined by recognizing it as an official or working language of international organizations or conferences (UN, UNESCO and other organizations).

It is recognized as one of the six official languages of the UN. Language refers to social phenomena that exist in all eras of human society. The main purpose of language is to serve as a communication tool. Language is inextricably linked with thinking, human consciousness, serves as a means of forming and expressing our thoughts and feelings.

There are more than 2000 languages on our planet. Among them, the Russian language is one of the most common. Despite the fact that languages are different from each other, each of them has "kinship" among other languages. The Russian language also belongs to the Ukrainian and Belarusian East Slavic family. The Russian language exists and is still developing because it performs all the universal functions characteristic of any language at one time.

With the help of language, people communicate, give each other thoughts, feelings, knowledge about the world around us. Any word in our language is not just a collection of sounds; it has its own meaning content. And we think in the same terms. Therefore, language is closely related to thinking. In a developing country, the Russian language is not only a language, but also performs three functions.

First, the Russian language is the national language of the Russian people. He created wonderful monuments of art and literature, the language of science and culture. The structure of words, their meanings and interrelationships convey knowledge about the world and people to others.

Secondly, the Russian language is the state language of the Russian Federation. During the existence of the USSR, such a language did not exist in Russian. Now it is a language that serves the needs of people not only at work, but also at home, the official language of the state, science, production and, of course, culture.

Thirdly, the Russian language is one of the international languages. It is one of the world languages declared official and working languages authorized by the UN in international relations.

Development of science and technology, art is impossible without the language life of a person, people, society. The meaning of language (speech, word) is emphasized by many Russian proverbs. Since the middle of the 20th century, the Russian language has become a well-known world language. In addition to Russian, any document in the UN is distributed in English, French, Spanish, Chinese and Arabic. Today, about 300 million people speak Russian. The richness of the Russian language and the literature created in it arouses interest in this language throughout the world. It is studied not only by students, schoolchildren, but also by adults. In 1967, the International Association of Teachers of Russian Language and Literature was established in Paris to teach the Russian language abroad. The association is publishing for foreign teachers of Russian language and literature, international olympiads in the Russian language among schoolchildren of different countries for methodical literature.

In the 16th and 17th centuries, Europeans learned such words as kremlin, kaftan, kopek, pista, kvass. A legend of a slave to a famous Greek philosopher; "One day Xanthus ordered Aesop to cook food from the worst thing in the world. The next day Xanthus now ordered food from the best thing in the world. Aesop again cooked food from the tongue. Xanthus asked why he cooked food from the tongue when he told him to cook food twice. Then Aesop He replied that it is the tongue that says the worst and the best." From this we can see that it is not only necessary to learn different foreign languages well, but also to know how to speak politely and politely in whatever language you speak.

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